

En Gedi sanctuary

also known as “En Gedi temple”, “En Gedi shrine”, “En Gedi mortuary shrine”

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Entry tags: Peak Sanctuaries, Temple, Levantine Religion, Prehistoric Religion, En Gedi temple, Religious Group, Religious Place, Religious Complex, Temenos, Sacred Enclosure, Chalcolithic, Mortuary shrine

The En Gedi cultic complex is one of several important places providing evidence for understanding the religious beliefs and practices of “Ghassulian” communities during the Chalcolithic (other important sites include Teleilat Ghassul, Gilat, the Cave of the Treasure, and Shiqmim). The cultic complex is located on a rocky promenade 700 m above the En Gedi oasis on the west bank of the Dead Sea and was first identified by Y. Aharoni in 1956 during survey and later excavated under J. Naveh (1957), B. Mazar (1961) and D. Ussishkin (1962, 1964). The site’s layout comprises two rectangular buildings whose entrances face inward toward a circular stone installation in the center of an open courtyard, and a stone fence connecting these structures with two entrance points, one of which contains evidence for a door (Ussishkin 1980: 4-14). The artifact assemblage is non-domestic in nature, consisting predominantly of different sized bowls, cornets, ibex and deer horn, goat bones, non-marine mollusks, and partial figurines of a bull laden with two churns and a serpent (Ussishkin 1980: 18-26; Gilead 2002: 110-111). Architecturally the layout is similar to the early Chalcolithic Area E temple at Teleilat Ghassul (Bourke 2001) and the EB I temple at Megiddo (Ussishkin 1980:29, with references; 2014). Unfortunately, no radiocarbon dates were collected during excavation resulting in debates over when the complex was constructed and abandoned (compare Ussishkin 1980:29-30 to Gošić 2016: 875-876). However, the presence of an alabaster jar imported from Egypt typologically dates to the fourth millennium BCE supporting a later date of (re)occupation (Ussishkin 1980: 21-25, with references). The function of the En Gedi cultic complex and its associated practices remain debated. The excavator interpreted the larger building as a sanctuary/temple and the smaller building as a priests’ quarters/storeroom (Ussishkin 1971, 1980, 2014). While the site lacks any actual evidence of storage, Ussishkin (1971:38-39; 1980; 2014) maintained the hoard of 400+ copper objects from the Cave of the Treasure at Nahal Mishmar, 10 km south of En Gedi, was the cultic equipment hidden by the En Gedi temple priests during their abandonment of the site (Ussishkin 1971, 1980). In terms of cultic practices, the circular stone installation has generated debate on whether it was linked to ritual practices associated with water cult (Ussishkin 1980: 34-35) or marked the place of a sacred tree (Mazar 2000; Chanteau 2014). Various proposals have also discussed the possibility of a deity being worshipped on site, rendering the En Gedi cultic complex as place of pilgrimage (e.g., Ussishkin 1980: 37, 2014; Amiran 1981; Gilead 2002; Arav 2014; Gošić 2016). Another proposal by D. Ilan and Y. Rowan (2015) builds from theory that central places are part of larger landscapes and seeks to understand En Gedi within its Judean Desert context (see also Rowan and Ilan 2007 and Ilan and Rowan 2012). They propose the Judean Desert formed a mortuary landscape wherein the En Gedi complex functioned as a mortuary shrine for the preparation and associated rituals connected with the primary burial of the dead in the Judean Desert caves (Ilan and Rowan 2015: 182, 184). Noting the combination of mortuary shrine and funerary landscape on the west side of large body of water is a practice attested in Egypt during the Predynastic, they raised the question whether “one culture group inform(ed) the other?” (Ilan and Rowan 2015: 184). This question was further explored, developed, and supported by N. Ben-Marzouk (2020). The En Gedi cultic complex is therefore not only important for understanding the Chalcolithic practices and religious beliefs of communities in the southern Levant, but also potentially how these practices may have influenced—or been practiced by—communities in contact.

Date Range: 4000 BCE - 3800 BCE

Region: Judean Desert oasis

Region tags: Israel

West Bank of the Dead Sea

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Ussishkin, D. 1980. "The Ghassulian Shrine at En-Gedi." *Tel Aviv* 7 (1-2):1-44.
- Source 2: Ussishkin, D. 2014. "The Chalcolithic Temple in Ein Gedi: Fifty Years after Its Discovery." *Near Eastern Archaeology* 77 (1):15-26.
- Source 3: Ilan, D., and Y. M. Rowan. 2015. "The Judean Desert as a Chalcolithic Necropolis." *Journal of Mediterranean Archaeology* 28 (2):171-194.

Reference: Arama, Milena Gošić. "Temples in the Ghassulian Culture: Terminology and Social Implications". *Етноантрополошки Проблеми*, Н. С. Год. 11, no. 3 (January 1, 2016): 869-93.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

- Scientific

Years of excavation:

- Year range: 1956 (survey), 1957 (test trench); 1961-1964 (excavation of site)

Notes: See: Aharoni, Y. 1958. "Archaeological Survey of `Ein Gedi." *Bulletin of the Israel Exploration Society* 22:27-45 (Hebrew). Naveh (Levi), J. 1958. "Chalcolithic Remains at `Ein-Gedi." *Bulletin of the Israel Exploration Society* 22:46-48 (Hebrew). Naveh, J. 1957. "Notes and News. `En Gedi." *Israel Exploration Journal* 7:264. Ussishkin, D. 1980. "The Ghassulian Shrine at En-Gedi." *Tel Aviv* 7 (1-2):1-44.

Name of excavation

- Official or descriptive name: Hebrew University expedition to En Gedi; En Gedi excavation project

Notes: For the history of survey and excavations, see: Aharoni, Y. 1958. "Archaeological Survey of `Ein Gedi." *Bulletin of the Israel Exploration Society* 22:27-45 (Hebrew). Naveh (Levi), J. 1958. "Chalcolithic Remains at `Ein-Gedi." *Bulletin of the Israel Exploration Society* 22:46-48 (Hebrew). Naveh, J. 1957. "Notes and News. `En Gedi." *Israel Exploration Journal* 7:264. Ussishkin, D. 1980. "The Ghassulian Shrine at En-Gedi." *Tel Aviv* 7 (1-2):1-44. Ussishkin, D. 2007. "The Ghassulian Shrine at En-Gedi." In *En Gedi Excavations I: Final Report (1961-1965)*, edited by E. Stern, 29-68. Jerusalem: Israel Exploration Society.

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

—Elevation

Type of elevation

—Hill

—Rock face

Notes: Located on a rock terrace approximately 700 feet in elevation overlooking the Dead Sea (Ussishkin 1971: 25-26) Ussishkin, D. 1971. "The "Ghassulian" Temple in Ein Gedi and the Origin of the Hoard from Nahal Mishmar." *Biblical Archaeologist* 34 (1):23-39.

—Water source

Notes: D. Ussishkin (1980:3) argues for the importance of water cult as the two entrances to the site are oriented toward the springs at En Gedi and En-Shulamit, less than a 10 minute walk from the architectural complex. A drain feature was also discovered in the stone fence enclosing the ritual space; Ussishkin proposed this feature may have once had a mud brick channel extending toward the circular stone installation in the center of the courtyard, which he believed was plastered and held water from the springs for on-site cultic practices (Ussishkin 1980: 10, 2014:20). Moreover, the rocky terrace selected to build the sanctuary faces southeast toward the Dead Sea, emphasizing the importance of water for this community (Ussishkin 1980:4). Ilan and Rowan (2015: 182) have connected the importance of water for this site to a larger Chalcolithic ideology that seems to have centered on the life cycle.

—Tree, grove, or forest

Notes: A. Mazar (2000) proposed the circular feature in the courtyard was to enclose a sacred tree, which would have given the site its significance. This proposal was rejected by Ussishkin (2014: 21) on the basis of the stone installation not being big enough to fit a large tree and that the bottom of the stone feature appeared to be natural ground. However, Julien Chanteau (2014) has attempted to reconstruct the architectural phases in which the broad room structures, gates, and fence were constructed. Noting that the excavation report indicates the fence was built after the structures, Chanteau analyzed the orientation of the first stage of structures around the circular stone feature in the center of the courtyard. Entertaining Mazar's proposal, he argued that the En Gedi structure—that is, all parts of the ritualized space—seem to be oriented toward this circular feature, which would make sense if it marked a tree. This proposal was then explained by connecting the tree with Eliade's concept of the axis mundi, wherein cross-cultural analysis demonstrates cosmic trees tend to mark the center of the universe (Chanteau 2014: 518-519). As such, this analysis of the phases of construction seeks to support Mazar's original proposal that the tree gave the space its ritual significance. M. Gošič

(2016: 873) has also rejected this proposal based on her argument that a tree needs a water source and the springs are too far away. See: Chanteau, Julien. 2014. "The Chalcolithic Shrine at En-Gedi. Aesthetics – Symbolism – Structure." In Proceedings of the 8th International Congress on the Archaeology of the Ancient Near East 30 April – 4 May 2012, University of Warsaw. Volume 3. Archaeology of Fire, Conservation, Preservation and Site Management, Bioarchaeology in the Ancient Near East, Islamic Session, Selected papers from workshop sessions, edited by P. Bieliński, M. Gawlikowski, R. Koliński, D. Lawecka, A. Soltysiak and Z. Wygnańska, 511-528. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz. Mazar, Amihai. 2000. "A Sacred Tree in the Chalcolithic Shrine at En Gedi: A Suggestion." Bulletin of the Anglo-Israel Archaeological Society 18:31-36. Ussishkin, David. 1980. "The Ghassulian Shrine at En-Gedi." Tel Aviv 7 (1-2):1-44. Ussishkin, David. 2014. "The Chalcolithic Temple in Ein Gedi: Fifty Years after Its Discovery." Near Eastern Archaeology 77 (1):15-26.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

- Leveling of ground
- Clearing
- Trackway or road-surface
- Water feature

Notes: Presumably modification to the local environment occurred for the construction of a stone pathway leading into the structure referred to variously as the "lateral chamber" (Ussishkin 1980:7) or "lateral room" (Ussishkin 2014:17). A drain outlet was also detected in the stone fence, suggesting it was connected to a water feature (Ussishkin 1980: 11-12, 17, 2014: 20) See: Ussishkin, David. 1980. "The Ghassulian Shrine at En-Gedi." Tel Aviv 7 (1-2):1-44. Ussishkin, David. 2014. "The Chalcolithic Temple in Ein Gedi: Fifty Years after Its Discovery." Near Eastern Archaeology 77 (1):15-26.

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– No

Notes: The En Gedi sanctuary is generally believed to have been located away from permanent Chalcolithic settlements, resulting in the proposal the site served as a place of pilgrimage to nomadic groups, as well as those of the Ghassulian culture (Ussishkin 1971, 1980:34, 41, 2014: 21; Arav 2014). However, the excavation of Moringa Cave located 400 m below the sanctuary raises the question what was the relationship between sites (Porath et al. 2007). Indeed, D. Ilan and Y. Rowan (2012, 2015) have proposed the site served as a regional mortuary complex servicing the

communities who buried their dead in the Judean Desert caves—some of which contained evidence of domestic use. See: Arav, R. 2014. "The Chalcolithic Temple in Ein Gedi—Some Anthropological Considerations: An Appendix to Ussishkin's Article." *Near Eastern Archaeology* 77 (1):27–31. Ilan, D., and Y. M. Rowan. 2012. "Deconstructing and Recomposing the Narrative of Spiritual Life in the Chalcolithic of the Southern Levant (4500–3600 B.C.E.)." *Archaeological Papers of the American Anthropological Association* 21 (1):89–113. Ilan, D., and Y. M. Rowan. 2015. "The Judean Desert as a Chalcolithic Necropolis." *Journal of Mediterranean Archaeology* 28 (2):171–194. Porath, R., A. Frumkin, U. Davidovich, Itzhaq Shai, and Hanan Eshel. 2007. "The Moringa Cave at the En-Gedi Oasis." *Qadmoniot* 40 (133):27–31. Ussishkin, D. 1971. "The "Chassulian" Temple in Ein Gedi and the Origin of the Hoard from Nahal Mishmar." *Biblical Archaeologist* 34 (1):23–39. Ussishkin, D. 1980. "The Ghassulian Shrine at En-Gedi." *Tel Aviv* 7 (1–2):1–44. Ussishkin, D. 2014. "The Chalcolithic Temple in Ein Gedi: Fifty Years after Its Discovery." *Near Eastern Archaeology* 77 (1):15–26.

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: While there is no evidence of permanent habitation in the region, various caves pepper the Judean Desert landscape, have evidence of domestic activity, and were used by communities to bury their dead (Ilan and Rowan 2015). Indeed, the so-called Cave of the Treasure in Nahal Mishmar is only 10.5km south of En Gedi, which led Ussishkin (1971, 1990, 2014) to propose the hoard of over 400 copper objects hidden in the cave was the ritual paraphernalia of the En Gedi temple.

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– Yes

Notes: It should be noted, however, that the place is situated away from more permanent habitation settlements. The site is located close to the caves in the Judean Desert, which yield evidence of both domestic habitation and burials during the Chalcolithic. Moreover, domestic refuse was found in the Moringa Cave dated to the Chalcolithic (Porath et al. 2007)

↳ Is there an established route of travel connecting it to a wider transportation network:

– Yes

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: In the center of the courtyard was a circular stone feature measuring 90cm wide and 40cm deep. Flat stones were placed vertically along the circumference of the circle. This feature was argued by the excavator to have been plastered and potentially used for water (Ussishkin 1980, 2014). Conversely, this feature was also argued to have marked the place where a sacred tree once stood (Mazar 2000; Chanteau 2014).

– Water channel

Notes: A feature interpreted as a water drain was excavated from the stone fence demarcating the sanctuary complex (Ussishkin 1980)

A group of structures:

– Yes

Notes: The En Gedi cultic complex comprises a stone fence linking two entrance points, a larger broad room structure interpreted as a sanctuary/temple, and a second broad room structure referred to as the "lateral chamber" or "lateral room." In the center of the courtyard is a circular pit 40 cm in depth and 90 cm in diameter. The pit is lined with vertically placed stones and then marked with stones radiating around its circumference, resulting in the entire installation measuring 3m in diameter. The gateway entrance at the southern point of the complex faces the En Gedi spring and contained a door socket on the outer entrance leading into a room where stone benches lined the walls. The second entrance point to the site faces the En Shulamit spring and did not contain an enclosed room but rather a gap in the stone fence with no evidence for a door. The larger broad-room structure contained an entrance with evidence of a door along the center of its long wall and benches inside and outside facing the courtyard. Directly opposite the door upon entering the larger broad room building—referred to as the sanctuary—was a large semicircular stone structure interpreted as an altar, within which was found ash, bones, a ceramic animal figurine of a possible bull(?) with two churns on its back, and the fragments of a possible serpent figurine. On the NE side of this semicircular feature, a round limestone drum-like feature was installed, interpreted by D. Ilan and Y. Rowan (2012:94) and the as the actual altar. Notably, the excavator indicated the limestone was not available in the immediate vicinity and thus was presumably brought to the site from elsewhere. On the eastern and western sides of the broad room structure, pits were dug into the ground and used as favissae for the discard of various material presumably used in rituals in the structure (these pits contained broken vessels and ibex horns). A second building referred to as the lateral chamber was a rectangular structure measuring 7.5 x 4.5m. The structure contained a stone lined path leading to its entrance, which shows signs that it too contained a door. A bench was built on the outer wall, facing the courtyard; however, no benches were constructed inside of this building (and thus, different from the other larger broad room structure) (Ussishkin 1980:4-11) See: Ilan, David, and Yorke M. Rowan. 2012. "Deconstructing and Recomposing the Narrative of Spiritual Life in the Chalcolithic of the Southern Levant (4500-3600 B.C.E)." Ussishkin, David. 1980. "The Ghassulian Shrine at En-Gedi." Tel Aviv 7 (1-2):1-44.

Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

Notes: It should be noted that the excavator states the 2 broad room buildings and the gates were built first, followed by the construction of the gate (Ussishkin 1980:11)

A group of features:

– Yes

Notes: Inside the broad-room sanctuary is located a semi-circular stone feature interpreted as an altar. A large, circular stone made of non-local limestone is embedded into the alter where it meets the northern wall of the building; it was interpreted as a cult stand by the excavator (Ussishkin 1980).

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– I don't know

Notes: The excavator notes that the two broadroom structures and the gates were constructed first, followed by the gate (Ussishkin 1980: 11). Presumably the internal layout of the broadroom was designed as such in its initial phase, but there is not enough information to say with certainty.

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: The four architectural structures combine with stone fence and the circular stone installation in the courtyard to form the En Gedi sanctuary (Ussishkin 1980)

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Social

Notes: How one interprets the complex shifts how one interprets its function. Ilan and Rowan (2015) maintain it served as a mortuary shrine for the preparation and associated rituals with the burial of the dead in the Judean Desert caves. The function would have thus been social/memorial

– Worship

Notes: If one interprets the complex as a temple, it may have thus served as a place of pilgrimage to worship a divine entity (e.g., Ussishkin 1980; Arav 2014). Notably, proposals that both a water cult and the marking of a sacred tree are two natural elements associated with the cult of the goddess. The

↳ Worship:

– Communal

Notes: Given that the location of the site is far from any permanent settlement, if the site served as a temple it is likely that the site served as a place of pilgrimage for certain community/communities (e.g., Ussishkin 1980; Arav 2014)

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is not enough information to answer this question

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: There is evidence in the larger broadroom structure of a miniature revetment added in the northwest corner as the extensive pits had begun to undermine the integrity of the structure, however the excavator notes that this is the only real evidence of modification and thus argues for a short habitation period of the site (Ussishkin 1980: 29)

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

Notes: There is no evidence to suggest the cultic complex was destroyed. Rather, the lack of material excavated from the site led the excavator to interpret the site was abandoned (Ussishkin 1980, 2014).

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

Notes: In antiquity I do not believe there is evidence to suggest any part of the site was reconstructed. However, I. Dunayevsky reconstructed the En Gedi sanctuary (Ussishkin 1980, Fig. 4)

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Given that there is debate on how the site functioned, the nature of the evidence is such that we cannot say with certainty whether the worship of/communication with non-human super nature beings occurred here. Chalcolithic religion appears centered on the regeneration of life (see Ilan and Rowan 2012). If the site is interpreted as a temple where a divine entity was worshipped, the the fact that the two gateway entrances to the sanctuary are oriented to the two springs in the area seems to support proposals of a water cult at the site (Ussishkin 1980: 34-35). Alternatively, Mazar (2000) proposal that the circular stone installation in the center of the courtyard once demarcated a sacred tree would possibly suggest the worship of/communication with a fertility goddess during this time at En Gedi. Note, however, that Ussishkin (2014) has rejected this proposal on the basis that the 90cm diameter of the stone installation is too small to serve as a "flowerpot" for a large tree, as well as the fact that when it was excavated the bottom of the 40cm pit appeared to be natural ground. Nevertheless, if the site is interpreted as a temple/sanctuary, the presence of a possible cult stand in the larger broadroom building suggests a divine entity may have been worshipped/venerated. Ussishkin (1980:37)

propose the limestone drum may have held a cult stand similar to the basalt stands featuring prominent faces as first discussed by C. Epstein. If the site functioned as a mortuary shrine its possible some sort of ancestral cult practices took place on site, which could have included the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings. However, the evidence is ambiguous in this regard.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is not enough information to answer this question

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Ilan and Rowan's (2015) proposal that the site served as a mortuary complex for the treatment of the dead buried in the nearby caves of the Judean Desert raises the possibility of ritual practices related to ancestors. The question of divinity is unknown. Chalcolithic religious belief seems to have centered on the importance of the life-cycle (see Ilan and Rowan 2012 with references therein). Ilan, D., and Y. M. Rowan. 2012. "Deconstructing and Recomposing the Narrative of Spiritual Life in the Chalcolithic of the Southern Levant (4500–3600 B.C.E.)." *Archaeological Papers of the American Anthropological Association* 21 (1):89–113. Ilan, D., and Y. M. Rowan. 2015. "The Judean Desert as a Chalcolithic Necropolis." *Journal of Mediterranean Archaeology* 28 (2):171–194.

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Field doesn't know

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Groups:

– Priests

– Men

– Women

– Children

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Notes: Ostensibly, a specific group of people constructed the sanctuary complex. However, the specifics of who those people were remains unknown. The excavator attributed the site to the "Ghassulian culture" based on the ceramics assemblage, as well as the belief that the cache of copper objects from the Nahal Mishmar cave/Cave of the Treasure was a ritual assemblage from the temple (Ussishkin 1971, 1980). Conversely, D. Ilan and Y. Rowan (2015) propose the site served as the mortuary complex for the communities burying their dead in the caves of the Judean Desert. As such, this appears to be a community effort and thus it is likely that men, women, and children participated in the construction of the space. However, there simply is

not enough evidence to say this for certain.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is not evidence evidence to answer this question. It is hard to say whether the community that used this space conceptualized of divinity. Chanteau (2014) proposed a sacred tree—first proposed by Mazar (2000)—should be viewed as an axis Mundi and thus marking the space as sacred. According to this proposal, the presence of a cosmic tree (which remained debated) was the reason for constructing on this space.

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is not evidence evidence to answer this question

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is not evidence evidence to answer this question

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is not enough evidence available to answer this question.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: Unknown. There is not enough evidence available to answer this question. If D. Ilan and Y. Rowan (2012, 2015) are correct in their proposal that the site functioned as a mortuary shrine, then its possible burial in the Judean Desert was the primary purpose. The location was presumably ideal given its access to water as well as its proximity to many of the caves used for burial in the region. Other proposals include the presence of a cosmic tree (Chanteau 2014) and the elevation and location close to water sources (Ussishkin 1980).

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Notes: The En Gedi sanctuary predates the development of writing

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Notes: The En Gedi cultic complex comprises a stone fence linking two entrance points, a larger broad room structure interpreted as a sanctuary/temple, and a second broad room structure referred to as the "lateral chamber" or "lateral room." In the center of the courtyard is a circular pit 40 cm in depth and 90 cm in diameter. The pit is lined with vertically placed stones and then marked with stones radiating around its circumference, resulting in the entire installation measuring 3m in diameter. The gateway entrance at the southern point of the complex faces the En Gedi spring and contained a door socket on the outer entrance leading into a room where stone benches lined the walls. The second entrance point to the site faces the En Shulamit spring and did not contain an enclosed room but rather a gap in the stone fence with no evidence for a door. The larger broad-room structure contained an entrance with evidence of a door along the center of its long wall and benches inside and outside facing the courtyard. Directly opposite the door upon entering the larger broad room building—referred to as the sanctuary—was a large semicircular stone structure interpreted as an altar, within which was found ash, bones, a ceramic animal figurine of a possible bull(?) with two churns on its back, and the fragments of a possible serpent figurine. On the NE side of this semicircular feature, a round limestone drum-like feature was installed, interpreted by D. Ilan and Y. Rowan (2012:94) and the as the actual altar. Notably, the excavator indicated the limestone was not available in the immediate vicinity and thus was presumably brought to the site from elsewhere. On the eastern and western sides of the broad room structure, pits were dug into the ground and used as favissae for the discard of various material presumably used in rituals in the structure (these pits contained broken vessels and ibex horns). A second building referred to as the lateral chamber was a rectangular structure measuring 7.5 x 4.5m. The structure contained a stone lined path leading to its entrance, which shows signs that it too contained a door. A bench was built on the outer wall, facing the courtyard; however, no benches were constructed inside of this building (and thus, different from the other larger broad room structure) (Ussishkin 1980:4-11) See: Ilan, David, and Yorke M. Rowan. 2012. "Deconstructing and Recomposing the Narrative of Spiritual Life in the Chalcolithic of the Southern Levant (4500-3600 B.C.E.)." Ussishkin, David. 1980. "The Ghassulian Shrine at En-Gedi." Tel Aviv 7 (1-2):1-44.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: The two entrance gates to the site face two springs, suggesting an association with water (Ussishkin 1980)

– Yes

Notes: The circular stone structure in the center of the courtyard may have enclosed a tree (Mazar 2000; Chanteau 2014)

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: A stone fence connects all of the structures, enclosing them in a space that must be entered through one of the two gates.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The larger broad room building with the semi-circular altar and benches seems to form one of the more important buildings on site given the favissae, concentration of material, and the addition of benches which suggests different type of activity vs. the other spaces in the

sanctuary complex

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

Notes: The upper portions of the walls on stone foundation are believed to have been sun-dried mud brick (Ussishkin 1980:4-5)

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– Yes

↳ Sand

– No

Notes: The excavation report does not mention sand as a material used in the construction of the cultic complex (see Ussishkin 1980)

↳ Clay

– Yes

Notes: Clay and smaller stones were placed in between the spaces of the larger stones used to construct the walls of the complex, the stone pathway, and the gateway entrances (Ussishkin 1980:4-12)

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

Notes: A 2.7 cm piece of painted plaster was excavated from the water channel, found with non-marine mollusks. The plaster was decorated with two dark blue wavy lines and one pink wavy line. The presence of plaster from an installation led the excavator to propose it was likely that all the walls were plastered. The plaster showed evidence of two layers, indicated upkeep like what is attested from the contemporary site of Teleilat Ghassul in the Jordan Valley, where there is wall paintings of ritual specialists and evidence that the walls had been replastered 20 times (Ussishkin 1980:12, Fig.6, 2014: 16).

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

↳ Wood

– Yes

Notes: Carbonized wood was excavated along with ashy material from the pits dug into the sides of the broadloom sanctuary. While no evidence of wood used in a structural was collected from the excavation, stone sockles at the main gatehouse entrance, the broadloom, and the lateral room indicate these structures were likely closed with a wooden door. It is also assumed that wood was used in the roofing of these structures (Ussishkin 1980:7, 12-15)

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– I don't know

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– No

Notes: The darker stones used in the construction appear to have been locally sourced however the circular crystalline limestone base incorporated into the semi-circular stone structure in the sanctuary is not immediately available (Ussishkin 1980:10)

– Yes

Notes: Limestone and other materials for the majority of the construction appear to have been sourced locally

Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: It is believed that mud brick was used in the construction of the upper portions of the walls (Ussishkin 1980:4, 8, 13)

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

Notes: The only remnants of decoration are restricted to a painted plaster fragment excavated from the channel in the stone fence. The plaster is reported to have thick pink and blue wavy bands (Ussishkin 1980: 12). Painted plaster decoration lined the walls of a contemporary cultic structure at Teleilat Ghassul in the Jordan Valley, which contained figural depictions in a seemingly cultic ritual that contained architectural features similar to the sanctuary at En Gedi (Drabsch and Bourke 2014, 2019). As such, the excavator has proposed the presence of plaster at En Gedi may suggest the site was similarly decorated (Ussishkin 2014).

Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Field doesn't know

Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Field doesn't know

Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The lack of explicit decoration from the site means there is not enough evidence to answer this question. Notably, a bull figurine and possible serpent figurine were excavated from

the site (Ussishkin 1980: 20-21) but it is hard to say whether these were "decorative" in their setting

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

Notes: A painted plaster fragment was excavated from the channel and is reported to have thick pink and blue wavy bands (Ussishkin 1980: 12)

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– No

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is hard to say where specifically the decorated plaster originated as it was excavated from the water channel. Based on parallels from Teleilat Ghassul, its likely the decorated plaster was inside the sanctuary.

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

Notes: It has been suggested that a cult statue was placed on the round limestone base in the sanctuary (Ussishkin 1980:37).

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– No

↳ Are there wall paintings:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is not known from where the painted plaster originated. Painted plaster decorated the walls of certain structures at Teleilat Ghassul, so it is possible this was also the case at en Gedi (Ussishkin 1980: 12)

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Notes: The En Gedi sanctuary was largely devoid of iconographic finds. One exception is a ceramic figurine of a bull with two churns on its back was excavated from the ashy remains of the semi-circular stone feature where the excavator noted virtually no pottery remains were recovered and possibly two fragments of a serpent figurine found near the eastern pits in the sanctuary (Ussishkin 1980:20-21, 35, 38, Figs. 10:23-24 and 11). It is unknown, however, whether these were conceptualized as divine entities.

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: Notes: No burials were discovered at the En Gedi cultic complex

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is unclear whether worship of the dead occurred in this space, however if the function of this space was a mortuary shrine (Ilan and Rowan 2015: 181-185), it is possible associated mortuary rituals may have commemorated the dead.

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While no burials were present at En Gedi, Ilan and Rowan (2015: 182-183) have proposed the site served as a mortuary shrine connected to a larger Judean Desert necropolis where primary burials and Chalcolithic goods were found in caves peppered throughout the region. When viewed together, they suggest the combination of a mortuary shrine + necropolis situated on the west side of a large body of water seems to draw parallel to the later Nile valley practice of burying the dead on the western bank of the Nile river and raise the possibility of influence (Ilan and Rowan (2015: 182-184)—a proposal supported and further developed by N. Ben-Marzouk (2020). To support their proposal that the En Gedi may have served a mortuary shrine where the treatment of the dead took place, they discuss the nature of its assemblage, which is dominated by v-shaped bowls, fenestrated pedestals, horns, and cornets—objects found in contemporary mortuary assemblages. Moreover, they argue ceramic cornets played an important part of ritual for Chalcolithic communities, including where primary burial was practiced—most notably Gilat and Teleilat Ghassul (Ilan and Rowan 2015: 181-185). While they do not discuss this point, we might further support their proposal the site may have been used for the treatment of the body by highlighting the contents of the cornets, which contained beeswax residue (Namdar et al, 2009). While scholars debate the function of cornets, we should explore the possibility they were used in the preparation of the body, where such a use for beeswax is attested in predynastic contexts in Egypt where primary burial also occurred (e.g., Lebedev et al. 2021). Contacts with the Nile Valley communities is potentially suggested by the presence of an imported Egyptian alabaster vessel found near the circular stone installation in the center of the courtyard, which Ussishkin (1980: 21, 34-38) connected with water cult. According to Ilan and Rowan (2015: 181), the importance of water also would fit with the life-cycle religion of the Chalcolithic. Sources: Ben-Marzouk, Nadia. 2020. "Forged by Society: An Interregional Investigation into the Social Implications of Metallurgical Knowledge Transfer in the Southern Levant and Egypt (ca. 5000-3000 BCE)." PhD dissertation, Department of Near Eastern Languages and Cultures, University of California, Los Angeles. Ilan, David, and Y. M. Rowan. 2015. "The Judean Desert as a Chalcolithic Necropolis." *Journal of Mediterranean Archaeology* 28 (2):171-194. Lebedev, Albert T., Olga V. Polyakova, Viatcheslav B. Artaev, Maria B. Mednikova, and Eugina A. Anokhina. 2021. "Comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatography-high resolution mass spectrometry with complementary ionization methods in the study of 5000 year-old mummy." *Rapid Communications in Mass Spectrometry* 35:e9058. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/rcm.9058>. Namdar, Dvory, Ronny Neumann, Yuval Goren, and Steve Weiner. 2009. "The contents of unusual cone-shaped vessels (cornets) from the Chalcolithic of the southern Levant." *Journal of Archaeological Science* 36 (3):629-636.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: No burials were present on site. However, the En Gedi sanctuary is located approximately 10km from the Nahal Mishmar cave, where over 400 copper objects were found hidden in the back of a cave. The close proximity and assumed contemporaneity of these two sites has led several scholars to interpret the hoard as the ritual assemblage of a shrine or sanctuary (Moorey 1988; Goren 1995), possibly the En Gedi sanctuary complex (e.g., Ussishkin 1971, 1980, 2014; Ilan and Rowan 2015).

Are formal burials present:

– No

Notes: Note, however, primary burials seem to characterize the burials in the Judean Desert (Ilan and Rowan 2015)

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is not enough evidence to say whether a supreme god was present.

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are previously human spirits present:

– Field doesn't know

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The possibility of a water cult, sacred tree, and figurines of a bull and possible serpent raise the possibility of nonhuman supernatural entities

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Ussishkin (1980) cites the presence of benches and a limestone drum incorporated into the altar in the large room as places where cult statues/stands may have been placed. Partial figurines of a bull and a serpent were also excavated from the site.

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Field doesn't know

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

–specify: Unclear

Notes: There is not enough evidence to say with certainty the number of people present in rituals. While the site contained benches and an open courtyard, the fence limited the number of participants in the space

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

–specify: Unclear

Notes: There is not enough evidence to suggest the frequency of rituals

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Field doesn't know

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Its unclear if sacrifices took place. The bones of a goat and the horns of both ibex and deer were found on site.

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Notes: There is no evidence to suggest this is a practice that took place

Are material offerings present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While the site was relatively lacking in material, the building with the altar contained refuse pits in its eastern and western sides. Within the refuse pits was evidence of ceramic vessels and animal bones. Piece of an alabaster vessel from Egypt was also found in the courtyard, possible connected with liquid libations as part of a water cult (Ussishkin 1980: 34-38). It is unclear if this material was connected with ritual practices related to offerings or served another function.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Field doesn't know

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: Given the remote location of the sanctuary, it is believed it served as a site of pilgrimage (Ussishkin 1980; Arav 2014)

How strict is pilgrimage:

– field doesn't know

Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The remote location seems to suggest the site was planned in accordance with its location, which is removed from permanent domestic sites. Note, however, that as the nature of the site is debated, we simply do not have enough evidence to suggest pilgrimage was the cause of its foundation

Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Its possible that the site served as a mortuary shrine and thus was associated with events connected to the life cycle (Ilan and Rowan 2015).

Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– Yes

Are these routes maintained together with the place:

– No

Notes: There is no evidence to suggest maintenance of the routes connecting the En Gedi sanctuary with its broader Judean Desert landscape; however it is assumed that the knowledge of the route was maintained within the community that utilized this space

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is virtually no evidence for on-site storage and the majority of the ceramic vessels were open (serving) wares. There is not enough evidence to suggest these were connected with feasting, however.

Are festivals present:

– Field doesn't know

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Field doesn't know

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Field doesn't know

↳ Present part time

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While no evidence is present at En Gedi that would allow us to make claims about hierarchy on site, proxy data from Teleilat Ghassul, another contemporary Chalcolithic shrine in the Jordan Valley, allows us a glimpse into the possible rank between ritual leaders and ritual participants. From a cultic building at Teleilat Ghassul, a plaster fresco depicts eight figures of different scales and states of dress. Drabsch and Bourke (2019: 5-6) note that the arrangement of these figures is suggestive of rank between the cult leaders and the participants. This interpretation is founded on the difference in clothing and scale of the individuals, with larger figures wearing ornately decorated clothing and masks, and carry implements whereas the participants are depicted on a smaller scale and nude from the neck down. In this scene, Drabsch and Bourke (2019: 5) note these figures are walking toward an architectural complex

similar to that at Teleilat Ghassul and En Gedi and thus its possible such hierarchy/rank was also manifest at En Gedi. Drabsch, Bernadette, and Stephen J. Bourke. 2019. "Early Visual Communication: Introducing the 6000-Year-Old Buon Frescoes from Teleilat Ghassul, Jordan." *Arts* 8 (3). doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/arts8030079>.

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is not enough evidence to answer this question.

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Similar to the question regarding whether religious specialists belonged to a certain class/caste, hierarchy is only hinted at through the plaster frescoes at Teleilat Ghassul which suggests some level of rank given the artists decision to visually differentiate the figures in the scene based on scale and dress.

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is not enough evidence to answer this question. Ussishkin (1980) referred variously to the lateral chamber as a "priests' quarters" however, the lack of evidence for on-site storage and the remoteness of the location suggest the site was not inhabited on a permanent basis by religious specialists

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Learning and thus training are two important components to the continuity of practice in any community. However, these are notoriously hard to identify in the archaeological record. If it is likely that is this space was utilized by ritual specialists—as most believe—then it is likely that observation and perhaps peripheral participation in ritual activities likely took place here to ensure the continuity of cultic practice—whatever that may have been.

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It remains unknown for how long the cultic complex was in use and thus it is hard to say with certainty whether a formal institution was charged with its maintenance. However, the excavator notes that the space contains evidence suggesting its systematic abandonment (Ussishkin 1980: 39). As such, we might assume that its maintenance was overseen by this same group.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Field doesn't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: If the sanctuary served as part of mortuary complex (Ilan and Rowan 2015), then presumably mortuary cult services were provided for a community.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

Entry/Answer References

Reference: Source 1: Ussishkin, D. 1980. "The Ghassulian Shrine at En-Gedi." *Tel Aviv* 7 (1-2):1-44., Source 2: Ussishkin, D. 2014. "The Chalcolithic Temple in Ein Gedi: Fifty Years after Its Discovery." *Near Eastern Archaeology* 77 (1):15-26., Source 3: Ilan, D., and Y. M. Rowan. 2015. "The Judean Desert as a Chalcolithic Necropolis." *Journal of Mediterranean Archaeology* 28 (2):171-194., Arama, Milena Gošić. "Temples in the Ghassulian Culture: Terminology and Social Implications". *Етноантрополошки Проблеми*, Н. С. Год. 11, no. 3 (January 1, 2016): 869-93.